

D5.3 - Summary of the online stakeholder workshop

prepared for

WP5.2 –Potential Terrestrial Applications Investigation

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1 STAKEHOLDER WORKSHOP “From the MOON to EARTH”

The online stakeholder workshop, titled “From the MOON to EARTH – How water technologies developed for the Moon can help our everyday life on Earth” took place on 18th June 2024.

The workshop was part of WP5.2 - Potential Terrestrial Applications Investigation, aiming to identify market potentials for transforming LUXEX-developed technologies into valuable applications. With participants invited for their potential commercial interests, the workshop contributes to the market scan analysis for possible terrestrial applications.

1.1 Workshop advertisement

The workshop was advertised on LUXEX website, and on LinkedIn (see Figure 1).

To advertise the workshop, there was an introductory video prepared, inviting for the workshop.

Figure 1: Screenshots of the LinkedIn post and workshop information on the LUXEX website

1.2 Workshop agenda

Below there is an agenda of the online workshop.

10:00 Welcome

- Introduction to LUWEX project (**Paul Zabel, DLR**) incl. Q+A
- Water purification & storage subsystem (**Rachele Perelli, Thales Alenia Space**) incl. Q+A
- Water monitoring subsystem (**Karol Leluk, WUST**) incl. Q+A
- Tour de table session (ca. 2-3 minutes per partner. Each of the partner prepares one slide concerning area of expertise/field of activity relating to their enterprise)

11:15 – 11:20 Break

- Introduction to possible terrestrial application. Report presentation (**Karol Leluk, WUST**)
- Open Discussion
 - how to potentially develop the technology itself further
 - introduction into the market: pros and cons, steps
 - summary

13:00 End of Workshop

1.3 Presentations

In the first part of the workshop, three presentations were given, each followed by a Q&A session.

1.3.1 Introduction to LUWEX project

Paul Zabel from DLR gave “Introduction to LUWEX project” discussing context, project objectives, partners, expected outcomes and impacts, extraction and capturing process, experimental campaign, and dissemination, exploitation, and communication plan of the project (see Figure 2). Paul Zabel also presented Workshop’s focus within the context of the project scope (see Figure 3).

During the Q&A session, a question was raised about the next steps for developing the system. The response highlighted the goal of making the system more comparable to space hardware, contingent on securing funding. It was noted that while the purification system is already akin to space hardware, the liquefaction system currently would not be suitable for use in space. Future design evolutions aim to address size, weight, and other specifications to better align with space hardware requirements.

Background: Water on the Moon

- Water on the lunar south pole:
 - Confirmed ± 5 wt.% in regolith in Cabeus crater (PSR) by LCROSS mission.
 - Micro cold traps (which are more accessible) believed to have 0,1 – 1 wt.% water in the regolith.
 - Indications of local patches containing up to 20 wt.% water in the regolith.
 - NASA's VIPER Mission will look for other water sources near (but not in) Nubile crater.
- Current gaps¹:
 - Form, concentration, and distribution of water is not known.
 - Technologies to locate and characterize resources.
 - Feasibility of mining techniques and operations in PSRs not verified by ground environmental chamber tests.

¹ NASA - BRRP Planetary & Terrestrial Mining Symposium (PTMS) June 2021

Extraction and capturing process

- Design for extraction and water capturing chosen using simulations and trade-offs.
- A water extraction crucible and a cold trap capturing device are placed in a "dusty" TVAC.
 - Temperature = 80 – 100 K.
 - Pressure = 10e-6 mbar.
 - Crucible size = ≈ 30 cm x 30 cm.
 - Icy regolith simulant mass up to 15 kg.
 - Amount of water present 5 wt.%, 750 mL (baseline)
 - Presence of volatiles: CO₂ & Methanol

Project schedule

- | | | |
|---|---|--|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Requirements definition Preliminary design of subsystems and experiments | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Detailed design Manufacturing and procurement of hardware Development of ice-regolith and lunar raw water simulants | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Technology validation campaign Evaluation of experiment results Investigation of future terrestrial and space applications |
|---|---|--|

Expected Outcomes and Impacts

<p>Project Results</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Validated technologies Ice-Regolith simulant Lunar raw water simulant Experiment results 	<p>Medium-term outcomes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Further development of technologies towards flight hardware Simulants and data for excellent science 	<p>Long-term impacts</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Innovative ISRU technologies Contribution to European lunar exploration mission
<p>2022-2024</p>	<p>2024+</p>	<p>2030+</p>

Figure 2: Screenshots from the introduction presentation, by Paul Zabel

Figure 3: Project's scope and workshop's focus, Paul Zabel

1.3.2 The Water purification & storage subsystem

Rachele Perelli from Thales Alenia Space presented “The Water purification & storage subsystem” outlining the Water purification & storage (WPS) overview, WPS design, and WPS test results (see Figure 4 and Figure 5).

Figure 4: Screenshots from the presentation on Water Purification and Storage Subsystem by Rachele Perelli

During the Q&A session, a question was asked about the biggest challenge for implementation on the Moon. The response emphasized that the key challenges are developing technology suitable for the lunar surface, selecting appropriate materials, and effectively scaling the system up and down.

Figure 5: Picture of WPS subsystem integrated to LUWEX system at TUBS

1.3.3 Water monitoring subsystem

Karol Leluk from WUST presented “Water monitoring subsystem” (see Figure 6), discussing Water quality monitoring subsystem (WQMS) overview.

Figure 6: Screenshots from the presentation on water monitoring subsystem, by Karol Leluk, WUST

1.3.4 Other aspects

Besides the technical aspects, the presentation discussed key players in the global water purification equipment market, SWOT Analysis, commercialization aspects and potential risks.

1.3.4.1 Key players in the global water purification equipment market

- 3M Company
- Midea Group Co., Ltd.
- Culligan International Company
- Unilever PLC
- Coway Co., Ltd.
- O. Smith Corporation
- DuPont de Nemours, inc
- Kent RO Systems Ltd.
- Eureka Forbes Ltd
- Panasonic Corporation
- LG Corporation
- Pentair PLC
- BLUEWATER SWEDEN AB

1.3.4.2 SWOT Analysis

<p>STRENGTHS</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Innovations for determining water quality, joining the trend of monitoring water for harmful substances. 2. Proven phenomena on which the technology is based. 3. Project consortium (scientific team). 4. The purpose of technology is to satisfy basic human needs. 	<p>WEAKNESSES</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. No IP protection strategy, no state of the Art. 2. No commercialization model. 3. Low TRL of the Technology. 4. Lack of information in the Project materials (eg. website) about other possible Technology uses on the Earth. 5. Made tests of Technology without the use of dirty earthly water.
<p>OPPORTUNITIES</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Decreasing water resources - demand for such technology. 2. Market and social trends emphasizing this type of technologies as develop in LUXWEX. 3. European Green Deal, Fit for 55 Package. 4. Using the LUXWEX Project for advertising, marketing activities aimed at commercialization (obtaining a partner for further work on LUXWEX technology). 	<p>THREATS</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Competition of companies and another technologies. 2. Scaling (TRL increase) time and costs. 3. Long time commercialization and implementation process. 4. Possible patent infringements (third party rights).

1.3.4.3 Commercialization

It was noted that, there is no one universal water treatment system. In order to increase the chances of commercializing the technology, it is recommended:

1. Development of a technological offer and carrying out marketing activities.
2. Development of a patent protection and commercialization strategy.
3. Acquiring companies and potential end users of the technology.
4. Development of guidelines (technical, scientific) for a new implementation project based on LUXWEX Technology as and data from point 1 and 2 above background IP.
5. The pilot implementation. Performing a technological audit and developing guidelines (design assumptions, mass balances, heat balances, etc.) for pilot implementations. As a result will be received a functional and utility program and a feasibility study. The pilot implementation (successful) will contribute to the commercialization of the implementation of the Technology on the wide market

1.3.4.4 Risks

The discussed risks indicate that while the technological risk is low for technology implemented and tested on an industrial scale, the LUXWEX Project is currently at TRL 4, meaning there is still a risk of not reaching TRL 9, which is crucial for successful implementation. Implementing R&D project results involves discount risks related to the level of technology and typical business risks. Estimating this discount risk is vital for valuing the technology, especially for selling or licensing it for commercialization. At low TRLs, technological discount risk is predominant, whereas mature technologies face primarily business risks in the market. Currently, the discount risk for the LUXWEX technology is estimated at 30-40% due to its unproven status on a larger scale, despite the market being well understood. The technology represents a new product and manufacturing process in a known market, with no patent rights obstructing its implementation.

1.4 Tour de table

Following the introductory presentations, after the break, the next part of the workshop included Tour de table and introduction of guests.

Workshop participants (see Figure 7):

- Karol Leluk, Anna Jurga, WUST, LUWEX team
- Paul Zabel, Mateo Rejon Lopes, DLR, LUWEX team
- Giorgio Boscheri, Rachele Perelli, Thomas Fili, TASI, LUWEX team
- Barbara Imhof, Monika Brandić Lipińska, LIQUIFER, LUWEX team

- Tomasz Marciniszyn, Tech-Transfer Company
- Marcin Kolonko, IMGW - The Institute of Meteorology and Water Management (weather forecast, prediction when water is available on earth)
- Katarzyna Martewicz, Department of Economy and Promotion, Marshal’s office of the Lower Silesia
- Anna Kolonko-Wiercik, Wroclaw’s Municipal Water and Sewerage Company
- Giovanni Marchitelli, TASI
- Katarzyna Czepil, Wroclaw Technology Transfer Centre, Horizon Contact Point
- Aleksandra Turyńska, Wroclaw Technology Transfer Centre, Horizon Contact Point
- Brigitte Lamarze, ESA (water technologies, ISRU, water purification),
- Blandine Gorce, YGT in Life Support Systems, ESA (terrestrial applications, water treatment)

List of participants who were unable to take part in the workshop but reveal interest in LUWEX project progress:

- Maciej Sławiński, National Centre for Research and Development, Poland
- Hannah Sargeant, University of Leicester
- Ulrich Kuebler, Airbus
- Aude DeClerq, European Space Agency
- Małgorzata Hołyńska, Aude De Clercq, European Space Agency

Figure 7: Screenshots with workshop participants

1.5 Open Discussion

The focus of the open discussion was on the potential terrestrial applications of the water purification & water monitoring technologies developed with LUWEX project.

Unique selling points

During the stakeholder workshop, Brigitte Lamarze emphasized the need for a more detailed comparison between the LUWEX water purification technologies and current water purification systems. She pointed out that while the information provided was accurate, it lacked clarity on the specific advantages of LUWEX technologies over other purification systems. She stressed the importance of identifying and highlighting the unique selling points.

The discussion underscored the added value of LUWEX technologies and the need to thoroughly screen and analyze their specificities compared to existing solutions. Participants considered how these technologies could fit into various scenarios, such as integrating with existing water treatment plants or being implemented in new systems from scratch. The conversation acknowledged the potential for multiple systems to coexist and the necessity of advancing water recycling solutions.

Additionally, the workshop highlighted the importance of establishing specific use cases for LUWEX technologies. Attendees were asked for their thoughts on the potential of these technologies for terrestrial applications, aiming to gather diverse perspectives on their viability and advantages in different contexts.

Costs aspects

Marcin Kolonko raised a pertinent question about the cost of implementing the LUWEX water purification system. In response, Karol Leluk acknowledged the difficulty in providing a precise cost estimate at this stage. He explained that the current production scale, which is geared towards space applications, results in higher costs due to small throughput and the need to address issues related to mass and size. These factors are less of a concern for terrestrial applications.

Karol Leluk highlighted that series production would significantly reduce the production costs, making the system more affordable per cubic meter of purified water. He emphasized the necessity of conducting a SWOT analysis to better understand the potential and feasibility of LUWEX technologies for terrestrial applications. The initial implementation for demonstration purposes required relatively low material engineering efforts, but scaling up for widespread use would benefit from economies of scale.

Example of mountain facility

Karol Leluk shared an example of developing a water retention system for a mountain facility facing significant water issues. The mountain resort near Wroclaw experienced a high influx of tourists during hot summer days, leading to water shortages and the lack of toilet facilities on the mountain.

The initial solution involved transporting water containers by truck to provide water for handwashing and toilet use. However, the cost of building the necessary infrastructure was twice the value of the existing infrastructure. To address this, a more efficient system was proposed, which involved capturing rainfall, using a small filtering system, and producing greywater for handwashing and toilet use. This solution aimed to reduce costs and improve water management at the facility.

Potential in Lower Silesia

Participants also explored the practical applications of lunar-inspired water technologies in Lower Silesia. Anna Kolonko-Wiercik, representing municipal water treatment, highlighted the importance of continuous use for maintaining the functionality of water treatment technologies. This perspective underscores the need for sustainable and consistent implementation to ensure effective water treatment solutions in the region.

Karol expanded on this by discussing the potential for reclaiming valuable resources from wastewater, such as phosphate, nitrate, antibiotics, and pharmaceuticals. This approach not only addresses environmental concerns but also aligns with new European Commission wastewater directives aimed at reclaiming sub-

stances like hormones to enhance the overall effectiveness of wastewater treatment processes in Lower Silesia. These insights reflect a growing awareness and commitment to leveraging advanced water technologies developed for space missions to benefit everyday life on Earth, particularly in regions like Lower Silesia.

Water precipitation

Marcin Kolonko offered to connect Karol with contacts who could provide insights from Italy, Austria, and Germany, regarding their respective approaches to water management. This exchange highlights the workshop's collaborative spirit, aiming to gather diverse perspectives and expertise from across Europe.

One notable suggestion emerged regarding the LUWEX system, which could be utilized for pre-cleaning and purifying wastewater effectively. Participants proposed leveraging precipitation maps and collaborating with colleagues across different countries to develop a comprehensive roadmap. This roadmap would analyze precipitation patterns in regions across Europe, particularly focusing on the four countries participating in LUWEX. By pinpointing areas with both high and low water availability, stakeholders aim to demonstrate the system's potential benefits and feasibility in various environmental contexts.

Technology Readiness Levels

There was also discussion on advancing Technology Readiness Levels (TRL) and their practical applications. Giorgio Boscheri highlighted challenges in increasing TRL, emphasizing the transition from single prototypes in space to industrialization. The importance of testing environments—from labs to analog sites and eventually operational settings—was stressed for refining technologies and reducing costs and procurement times.

Participants queried Giorgio and Rachele on their experiences with TRL development. They noted that while TRLs traditionally relate to space, adapting them to terrestrial applications requires considerations like industrialization and testing in relevant environments. The analogy drawn to the EDEN ISS greenhouse, initially an analogue for space, later adapted for Antarctica, underscored the potential for technologies like LUWEX to first be developed for remote or extreme environments before wider applications.

The discussion explored logistical parallels in remote areas and highlighted opportunities for synergy between space-developed TRLs and terrestrial solutions. This approach aims to identify common challenges and solutions across different environments, including deserts and other remote regions, thereby maximizing the utility of advanced technologies originally conceived for space missions.

Other applications

The workshop participants explored diverse applications beyond conventional uses of water technology. They discussed organizing a hackathon aimed at brainstorming innovative scenarios for technology application, emphasizing creativity over technical specifics. Military applications emerged as a key focus, with considerations for scenarios involving restricted water access during conflicts, highlighting the potential for water treatment tools to mitigate such challenges.

Participants considered unconventional applications such as soil purification and water extraction from polluted terrains. These discussions underscored the workshop's proactive approach to exploring novel uses of advanced water technologies, including their adaptation to environments like deserts and contaminated areas.

Moreover, the idea of engaging students through competitions was proposed to foster new perspectives and ideas. This approach not only encourages innovation but also integrates the enthusiasm and fresh thinking of younger generations into solving real-world water management issues.

1.6 Summary

The workshop highlighted key insights into applying lunar-inspired water technologies on Earth. Emphasis was placed on identifying unique advantages of LUWEX purification systems, addressing cost efficiency through scaling, and exploring diverse applications in varied environments. Discussions on Technology Readiness Levels underscored the need for industrialization and practical testing, drawing parallels from space analogues. Recommendations included strategic steps for commercialization, such as patent protection and

pilot implementations, aiming to enhance global water management solutions. Overall, the workshop fostered innovative thinking towards leveraging advanced technologies to meet pressing water challenges, echoing Marcin Kolonko's sentiment that "Water plays the role of gold" in modern society.